

Table 2. Percentage of tillers with AfRGM galls at 63 DAT (mean + standard error) at four trial locations, 1997.

Entry ^a	Ogidiga, southeast Nigeria	Gadza, central Nigeria	Karfiguéla, Burkina Faso	Longorola, Mali
<i>sativas</i>				
ITA306 (check)	24.2 + 1.14	14.5 + 0.67	31.9 + 2.58	3.7 + 0.66
TOS9285	11.7 + 1.32	14.9 + 4.25	21.9 + 2.45	1.8 + 0.57
TOS3563	12.9 + 3.63	8.0 + 1.47	20.0 + 0.91	2.0 + 1.07
TOS11530	12.2 + 1.21	1.8 + 0.65	21.8 + 3.78	4.6 + 1.42
PTB12	13.0 + 3.52	1.5 + 0.42	21.6 + 1.14	3.2 + 0.47
Nhta 8	16.4 + 1.99	9.9 + 5.82	8.7 + 1.89	2.9 + 0.24
TOS3546	11.7 + 1.18	1.7 + 1.02	20.0 + 1.93	2.5 + 0.29
Aganni	10.6 + 1.70	13.0 + 2.47	6.5 + 1.63	2.8 + 0.32
Checkhalopiretal	11.5 + 5.12	5.5 + 2.47	8.9 + 1.51	5.1 + 0.73
Veluthacheera	5.8 + 1.53	3.5 + 1.44	10.9 + 2.32	1.4 + 0.93
TOS14519	2.2 + 0.41	1.1 + 0.85	2.9 + 2.05	2.3 + 0.95
All <i>sativas</i>	12.0	6.9	15.9	2.9
<i>glaberrimas</i>				
TOG6730	0.0 + 0.00	2.0 + 0.42	14.6 + 1.76	2.6 + 0.64
TOG6539	0.0 + 0.00	3.7 + 1.64	12.7 + 3.88	2.7 + 1.04
TOG6472	0.0 + 0.00	1.7 + 0.60	14.6 + 0.40	2.6 + 0.70
TOG7206	0.0 + 0.00	2.1 + 1.15	13.5 + 1.10	2.9 + 0.05
TOG6342	0.0 + 0.00	0.5 + 0.30	14.1 + 0.44	2.7 + 0.82
TOG6489	0.0 + 0.00	0.9 + 0.49	15.0 + 0.83	0.8 + 0.15
TOG6216	0.0 + 0.00	1.1 + 0.32	7.0 + 3.74	1.5 + 0.85
TOG6346	0.0 + 0.00	1.5 + 0.70	5.2 + 2.85	1.9 + 0.51
TOG7106	0.0 + 0.00	0.9 + 0.56	2.0 + 0.95	1.7 + 0.47
All <i>glaberrimas</i>	0.0	1.6	11.0	2.2

^a*sativas* and *glaberrimas* are listed in the order of mean infestation level across all sites.

tive to the check and to each other. Analyses of variance on the arc sine-transformed percentages showed that the interaction between rice variety and location effects was highly significant (1996: F = 9.89, df

= 75 and 180, $P < 0.001$; 1997: F = 7.51, df = 57 and 152, $P < 0.001$). The most marked difference between locations was in the resistance levels shown by the *glaberrimas* relative to the *sativas*. The *glaberrimas*

were much more resistant than the *sativas* in southeast Nigeria and Sierra Leone. In central Nigeria, most *glaberrimas* were only moderately resistant (1-5% infestation), whereas in Burkina Faso many were susceptible (>10% infestation) although still, on average, better than the *sativas*. In Mali, there was even less difference between the two species. More data are needed from this location, however, because of the low AfRGM pressure in both years.

Although small differences between locations may be due to environmental effects, such large and consistent variety \times site interactions strongly suggest that AfRGM populations at different locations have genetic differences that affect their abilities to overcome resistance. The results have important implications for future screening and breeding work on AfRGM and highlight the need to screen more *glaberrimas* in Burkina Faso and Mali. Some entries, in particular TOS14519 and TOG7106, appeared to have relatively stable resistance across locations, but these need to be tested further. The WARDA IPM Task Force is continuing this study to identify sources of stable resistance and investigate variation in AfRGM populations.

Resistance to rice stripe virus in differential rice line BL 1

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Rice stripe virus (RSV) is the most important viral disease of rice in temperate rice-growing countries such as China, Japan, and Korea. Almost all lowland cultivars with RSV resistance in Japan have the *Stvb-i* gene, introduced from the Pakistan indica cultivar Modan. Because the appearance of new strains able to overcome this gene threatens these varieties, sources of resistance to RSV must be diversified.

BL 1 is an elite germplasm line with the blast resistance gene *Pi-b* and has been used as a differential line for testing the pathogenicity of blast fungus. It was bred by backcrossing the Japanese cultivar Norin 25 with the Indonesian cultivar Tjina to introduce blast resistance from indica to japonica.

Tjina, BL 1, and F₁ plants from a cross between Nipponbare and BL 1

showed no symptoms in a field test for RSV resistance, although the average infection percentage of susceptible cultivars Nipponbare and Norin 25 was 92.6% (Table 1). BL 1 and its donor parent for blast resistance, Tjina, were highly resistant to or symptomatically tolerant of RSV infection in the field. In a test for resistance to the RSV vector, the smaller brown planthopper (SBPH), *Laodelphax striatellus*, the total

Table 1. Resistance to RSV in field and artificial inoculation tests.

Line/F ₁	Percent infection	
	Field ^a	Inoculation ^b
Norin 25	92.4 + 1.5 b	90.2 + 3.9 c
Tjina	0.0 + 0.0 a	(no data)
BL 1	0.0 + 0.0 a	41.1 + 4.2 b
Nipponbare	90.9 + 2.6 b	94.9 + 4.5 c
Nipponbare/BL 1(F ₁)	0.0	63.6

^aData are means + SEM of three replicates. Nipponbare/BL 1 (F₁) and BL 1 were tested without replication. SEM = standard error of means.

^bData are means + SEM of seven replicates. Nipponbare/BL 1 (F₁) were tested without replication. Means followed by the same letter within a column are not significantly different at $P = 0.05$ ($k = 100$) according to Waller-Duncan LSD.

number of nymphs on Nipponbare and BL 1 was significantly higher than that on IR50 (resistant check). We concluded that BL 1 was susceptible to SBPH, although resistant to RSV, and that Nipponbare was susceptible to both (data not shown).

The inheritance of RSV resistance was studied by artificial inoculation using viruliferous SBPH and by serological assay using an enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay. In the inoculation test on seedlings, the average infection percentage of RSV was 41.1 for BL 1, 94.9 for Nipponbare, and 63.6 for their F₁, suggesting that BL 1 resistance was incompletely dominant. The RSV incidence distribution in F₃ lines was multimodal with three peaks, indicating a single major genic segregation for resistance. To confirm this, we analyzed the

Table 2. Relationship between RSV resistance and blast resistance in F₃ lines from Nipponbare and BL 1.

RSV incidence	Number of F ₃ lines ^a	Number of F ₃ lines with reaction to blast isolate Ken 54-20	
20.0–80.0 ^b	148	Resistant	31
		Segregating	79
		Susceptible	38
		χ^2 (1:2:1) = 1.338	
80.1–100.0	52	Resistant	12
		Segregating	27
		Susceptible	13
		χ^2 (1:2:1) = 1.338	
		χ^2 (1:2:1) = 1.240	
χ^2 (3:1) = 0.107			

^aNo chi-square values for goodness of fit to expected ratios were significant. The uniformity test was also not significant for segregation for blast resistance between high and low RSV incidence groups ($c^2 = 0.104$, $0.90 < P < 0.95$, $df = 2$). ^bMaximum RSV incidence was determined from the range of the susceptible parent, Nipponbare.

mode of inheritance biometrically. We estimated that an incompletely dominant gene controlled BL 1 resistance based on maximum likelihood ratios. These results also agreed with the chi-square goodness of fit test to a ratio of 3 (homozygous resistant and segregating):1 (homozygous susceptible) as expected by segregation of a pair of incompletely dominant genes (Table 2).

The segregation of all F₃ lines fitted a ratio of 1:2:1 as expected by the segregation of the *Pi-b* resistance gene. No relation was seen between RSV infection incidence and the blast resistance gene *Pi-b* segregation in F₃ lines (Table 2). We concluded that the locus of RSV resistance in BL 1 was independent of the *Pi-b* locus, estimated to be near the terminal region of chromosome 2.

We observed many progeny susceptible or segregating for resistance to RSV in F₃ lines ($n = 72$) between BL 1 and Musashikogane with *Stvb-i*. The segregation pattern of 70 (homozygous resistant and segregating):2 (homozygous susceptible) in RSV resistance fitted a 15:1 ratio as expected based on the genetic model of the two independently dominant genes. From these results, we concluded that BL 1 has a new resistance gene for RSV infection with incomplete dominance not linked to the *Pi-b* locus. The new resistance gene identified in BL 1 with improved plant type and blast resistance is considered useful in breeding for RSV-resistant cultivars in japonica rice.

Ischaemum rugosum—a potential alternate host of rice tungro viruses in West Bengal

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Carry-over of rice tungro disease (RTD) through seasons is one of the most important considerations in rice production, especially in India where the vector green leafhopper (GLH) (*Nephotettix* spp.) ap-

pears for a limited period of the year. In West Bengal, in boro rice (summer rice), which is transplanted in February-March and harvested in April-May, RTD incidence is very limited and found only in a few

pockets with an intensive rice-rice rotation. To search for alternate RTD hosts, we collected leaf samples of some weeds from an adjacent field severely infected with RTD during the 1995-96 boro season in the